

A Study on Test Smells in JavaScript: Perceptions of the Developers.js

Topics

- **Objectives**
- **Examples**

Objectives

- Understanding the relevance of identifying bad practices in JavaScript test code.
- Understanding the perspective and feedback from developers.

Test Without Description (TWD)

Consider that your test case does not include a descriptive text. How does this issue impact the readability and understanding of the test case?


```
1 test("", () => {  
2     const result = getPermission();  
3     expect(result).toBe(true);  
4 });  
5
```

Anonymous Test (AT)

How does the absence of a clear description impact the readability and understanding of a test case?


```
1 test("should work", () => {  
2     const result = getAge();  
3     expect(result).toEqual(10);  
4 });  
5
```

Transcripting Test (TT)

How can the inclusion of logs, such as `console.log`, `console.warn`, or `console.info`, in a test case affect the readability, clarity, performance, and effectiveness of the tests?


```
1  test("Test 1", () => {
2    console.log("Logging to the console");
3    expect(someFunction()).toBe(true);
4  });
5  test("Test 2", () => {
6    console.warn("Warning message");
7    expect(anotherFunction()).toBe(false);
8  });
9  test("Test 3", () => {
10   console.error("Error message");
11   expect(anotherFunction()).toBe(false);
12  });
13
```

Comments Only Test (COT)

What is the impact on the maintenance and clarity of a test case that is completely commented out, without any executable test assertions?


```
1 // test("should work", () => {  
2 //   const result = getAge();  
3 //   expect(result).toEqual(10);  
4 // });  
5
```

Overcommented Test

What is the impact on the maintenance and clarity of a test case that has too many comments?

```
1 // Test to verify if the getUserInfo() function returns user information correctly
2 test("getUserInfo returns user information", () => {
3   // Calls the getUserInfo() function to obtain user information
4   const userInfo = getUserInfo();
5   // Equality-sensitive test: Compares the object returned by the function with an expected object using the toEqual() method
6   // This test verifies if all properties of the returned object are identical to those of the expected object
7   expect(userInfo).toEqual({
8     id: 1, // Checks if the id is 1
9     username: "john_doe",
10    email: "john@example.com", // Checks if the email is 'john@example.com'
11  });
12 });
13
```

Sensitive equality (SE)

What are the implications and challenges of using the `toString()` method to compare primitive types and data structures in tests, and how can this affect the accuracy and clarity of test results?

```
1  
2 test ('it should check user age to be equal to 13', () => {  
3     const user = getUser()  
4     expect(user.age.toString()).toEqual('13')  
5 })
```

General Fixture (GF)

What are the risks associated with using general fixtures (mocked data) in test cases, and how can this impact the reliability and independence of the tests?

```
1 let user;
2 let admin;
3 let guest;
4 beforeEach(() => {
5   user = new User("Alice", 30);
6   admin = new Admin("Bob", 40);
7   guest = new Guest("Charlie", 25);
8 });
9 test("user should have a name", () => {
10   expect(user.name).toBe("Alice");
11 });
12 test("admin should have an age", () => {
13   expect(admin.age).toBe(40);
14 });
```